

REDUCING DAMAGE NEAR CIRCULAR HOLES IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

The following considers the sensitivity of open-hole tension coupons to laminate fibre orientation. The effects are described numerically and experimentally using finite element analysis and Digital Image Correlation, respectively. Improvements in strength exceeding 10% suggest that tailoring fibre orientations may have potential to minimize the effect of strain concentrations.

Keywords: Image Correlation, Failure Criteria, Open-Hole-Tension, Damage, First-Ply-Failure

INTRODUCTION

Composite strength depends strongly on the layup and stacking sequence. A number of failure criteria have been applied to composites with circular-hole stress concentrations to predict strength. Much of the effort surrounding the effect of circular holes in composites concerns the interaction with the fastener. The limited work considering ply orientation has focused primarily on standard fibre directions.

Tay et al. examined open-hole tension laminates and showed that the pattern of damage progression in each ply depended on the stacking sequence [1]. Oh et al. examined stacking sequence variations of hybrid (carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy) composites [2]. As the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies were evenly distributed through the thickness, the bearing strength increased for all carbon to glass ratios. Park studied the effect of stacking sequence and clamping force on pinned and bolted joints, and found that designing a layup with 90° plies on the surface increased the delamination strength [3]. Ambu et al. found that fatigue strength benefited from delamination by decreasing the stress concentration at the hole which suppressed fiber failure [4]. Tan compared aluminum and graphite/epoxy specimens with circular hole stress concentrations [5]. Uniaxial laminates had a lower notched strength than aluminum, while multiaxial laminates had a higher notched strength.

The boundary conditions surrounding a stress concentration can have a large effect on strength. Yan et al. found that filled-hole laminates tended to fail by fiber-matrix splitting [6]. Oh found the opposite effect in bolted-joints, where delaminations were more prevalent [2]. Starikov et al. found that the tensile strength of bolted joints exceeded the compressive strength [7]. He also found that increasing the number of 0° plies improved both the tensile and compressive strengths. Yan et al. observed the same improvement in filled-hole tests [6]. He attributed the improvement to a reduction in the

stress concentration from fiber-matrix splitting. When clamp-up was introduced, strength decreased because fiber-matrix splitting was constrained. Yan also examined double lap bolted joints, and found that strength improved with clamp-up because the mode of failure was shifted from bearing to net-tension. Park found that this clamping pressure suppressed delamination onset and interlaminar crack propagation [3]. Oh found a similar result by varying the washer size [2].

A number of failure criteria have been applied to composites with circular hole stress concentrations to predict strength. Dano et al. considered the bearing response of pin-loaded graphite/epoxy composite plates [8]. He found that the maximum stress criterion predicted the strength of linear materials more reliably than the Hashin failure criterion; this difference lessened with non-linear materials. Shi numerically examined shear loading near the open hole of carbon/epoxy symmetric laminates [9]. Analytical results indicated that the energy density criterion was best suited for strength prediction because it accounted for all of the stress components. Tay et al. used the strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) and the element failure method (EFM) with finite element analysis to reflect the general state of damage and loading [1]. The SIFT-EFM approach was demonstrated for many test scenarios including open-hole tension, and allowed for both mechanical and environmental loading.

The following considered the effect of non-traditional layups and orientations on open-hole tensile strength. A FEA model was used to interrogate strains in the vicinity of the hole, from which failure criteria were compared to experiment. Spatial strain measurements were used to identify the onset of yielding near the hole and verify the numerical models.

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A 3D FEA model was constructed to obtain the strain surrounding the hold and consider edge effects. An eighth section was modelled using 8 noded solid brick elements (Solid64, Ansys) as shown in Fig. 1. Each ply was described by 2 elements through the thickness.

A standard quasi-isotropic layup $[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_s$ was used as a baseline, and was compared with non-traditional layups. The laminates were selected by sequentially altering one of the primary fibre orientations, as shown in Table 1. Laminates A, B, and D, for instance, modified only the 45, 90 and 0° ply, respectively, from the baseline layup. Laminate C kept the same orientation as the baseline, but modified the stacking

Fig. 1. Representative FEA mesh showing the hole surface.

Fig. 2. Normalized elastic properties of the composite laminates

The fibre orientation influenced the laminate elastic properties. The elastic response of the laminates is compared in Fig. 2, where they have been normalized with respect to the baseline laminate. Laminates A-F were selected to have an elastic response comparable to the baseline laminate, while laminates G-J were selected to consider the effect of relatively large changes in fibre orientation.

DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION METHOD

The digital image correlation method (DICM) was used to measure spatial strain fields. It is an optical technique that measures deformation by comparing images from an unloaded reference surface to a deformed surface. A high contrast speckle pattern was applied to the test surface prior to mechanical testing, as shown in Fig. 3. Recent advances in digital image processing have improved its accuracy and reliability. DICM has been used to describe strain gradients surrounding circular holes in dynamic [10, 11], static and fatigue loading [4]. Digital image correlation was found to effectively

Table 1. Ply orientations of the baseline and non-traditional layups. All laminates have 16 plies and are symmetric.

Designation	Layup
BL	$[(45/90/-45/0)_2]_s$
A	$[(54/90/-54/0)_2]_s$
B	$[(45/51/-45/0)_2]_s$
C	$[(45/0/-45/90)_2]_s$
D	$[(45/90/-45/57)_2]_s$
E	$[(54/54/-54/0)_2]_s$
F	$[(45/-45/90/0)_2]_s$
G	$[(21/90/-21/0)_2]_s$
H	$[(45/0/-45/0)_2]_s$
I	$[(\pm 45)_4]_s$
J	$[0]_{16}$

Fig. 3 Representative high contrast speckle pattern.

characterize failure modes and strain redistribution near the hole during failure progression. Since DICM is a surface technique its ability to describe interior strains deteriorates with delamination [4]. For the work considered here, images of the speckled region were taken using two high resolution video cameras (Vic-Snap, Correlated Solutions). The images were discretized and their displacements were mapped using commercial software (Vic3D, Correlated Solutions).

EXPERIMENT

Open-hole tension coupons measuring 12 x 1.5 x 0.07 in (305 x 38 x 1.8 mm) were formed from 16 plies of carbon/epoxy prepreg (T600/125-33). All coupons were autoclave cured at 350 °F (177C) and 90 psig (620 kPa). Four coupons were made for each layup. Endtabs were adhesively bonded to the gripped region to minimize grip failure. Three coupons of each layup were loaded to failure at 0.05 in/min (1.3 mm/min) to find the UTS. One coupon of each layup was given a high contrast speckle pattern and loaded at the same rate while images of the speckled surface were recorded at one frame every six seconds to 90% of the UTS.

Recording images of the speckled pattern from two cameras allowed the of out-of-plane displacements to be determined. While out-of-plane displacements are generally small, they occur from the Poisson effect and load frame misalignment. If neglected, out-of-plane displacements can cause error in the in-plane displacement measurements. The cameras were calibrated with a 3.99 mm spaced black dot grid. Images were acquired using CCD cameras (4 mega pixel resolution) with 50mm Schneider lenses. Displacements were found from the images using a subset of approximately 38, and the step size of approximately 12.

The longitudinal and transverse strength properties were obtained from [0] and [90] laminates, respectively. To decouple the elastic non-linear response from damage, the shear strength was obtained from successive load-unload tests of a [± 45] laminate as shown in Fig. 4. Between tests the coupons were allowed to recover. The permanent strain was plotted as a function of the maximum applied stress, as shown in Fig. 5, to determine the yield strength.

Fig. 4. Representative load-unload tests of a [±45] coupon.

RESULTS

Below 50% UTS, the measured stress-strain response of most laminates was linear. Over this linear range the elastic properties from experiment were found to agree with lamination theory (Fig. 2). Above 50% UTS, large strains were observed near the hole, as shown in Fig. 6. Softening was particularly evident when the shear strain was considered. The response was often bi-linear, allowing a coupon yield point to be

Fig. 5. Permanent strain as a function of shear stress of a [±45] test coupon.

Fig. 6. Representative stress-strain response near the hole edge.

defined as low as 25% UTS for some laminates. These results are in contrast to the common perception of brittle OHT strength.

The average yield point of each laminate was found using DICM and compared with common failure criteria in Fig. 7. The criteria included Maximum Strain [1], Energy [2], Tsai-Wu, Hoffman, and Tsai-Hill [3] and Puck. The good agreement provided by the maximum strain criterion is surprising, as it is typically associated with fibre dominated failure. It suggests that strain based failure criteria may have broad utility in describing both matrix and fibre dominated failure.

The non-traditional laminates were observed to have a measurable effect on the

Fig. 7. Comparison of the first-ply-failure strength with generalized failure criteria.

strength, which increased more than 10% over the baseline laminate in some cases. The relatively simple criterion of minimizing the strain concentration to select the fibre orientations of laminates A-D was surprisingly successful. While the strain concentration did not accurately capture the magnitude of the change in strength, it identified beneficial laminates for the fibre dominated coupons (A, B, D).

SUMMARY

The foregoing has considered the effect of laminate fiber orientations on the stress concentration in open-hole tension tests. The strength of a quasi-isotropic laminate was compared with variants which included altering each fiber orientation sequentially as well as the stacking sequence. The results appear promising, where in some cases the yield and ultimate strengths were more than 10% higher than the baseline. While yield properties are typically not considered in open-hole tension, they may be important as they were often 25% of the UTS. The DICM appears well suited in capturing the peak strain response, although it cannot be evaluated at the hole edge. The correlation of the yield strength with a maximum strain criterion was positive.

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